

Dissemination & Communication Plan for EmpoWomen Programme

Deliverable 4.1. Dissemination & Communication Plan

Prepared by: TechUkraine

Description

Dissemination, communication, and networking activities plan and guidelines for the project.

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Abbreviations

BAE	Business Angels Europe
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
No	Number
M	Month
R	Document, Report
SWG	Startup Wise Guys
T	Task
TU	TechUkraine / TechUA
WP	Work Package

I. Executive Summary

The present document is deliverable D4.1 – “Dissemination & Communication Plan”, framed within the EU-required WP4 – “Ecosystem Building & Exploitation” of the EmpoWomen project. The main objective of ecosystem building within the EmpoWomen project is to create and nurture a supportive and collaborative environment for women entrepreneurs, and to connect women with mentors, advisors, and resources that can help them succeed.

The deliverable aims to outline the strategy for dissemination and communication activities carried out during the project.

The D4.1. deliverable is structured in three sections. The first section describes the EmpoWomen project and its management structure. The second section covers the methodology, procedures, and obligations regarding communication and dissemination activities in the EmpoWomen project and the goals it pursues. Also, the second part of the document depicts the communication and dissemination strategy from the project to the external audience, target groups, and the dissemination tools and channels used for accomplishing project purposes. Further the deliverable features internal communication procedures and stipulates rules for the correct use of external communication and dissemination tools. Lastly, there are listed the elements needed to evaluate and measure the results of the communication strategy. In the third section there is a conclusion upon a suggested communication and dissemination strategy and plan.

The key objectives of the communication and dissemination plan for the EmpoWomen programme include raising awareness within the target audience about programme goals and tailoring communication strategies to specific groups. Clear messages are developed to effectively convey the programme's purpose. Stakeholder engagement focuses on collaboration with ecosystems and communities in widening area countries to enhance visibility and impact. Media relations aim to secure coverage through various channels, while maintaining a robust online presence via a dedicated website and social media platforms. Events and workshops serve to showcase achievements and create networking opportunities. The plan also includes implementing a monitoring and evaluation system for continuous improvement and adapting strategies over time.

About EmpoWomen Project

EmpoWomen originated to overcome barriers in digital and deep tech innovations led by women, aiming to enhance equality in the deep tech entrepreneurship sector. The goal is to establish an innovation loop that fosters collaboration among diverse European ecosystems and introduces a distinctive programme dedicated to scaling up women-led companies in the expanding geographical region.

The project will run two open calls for proposals to discover and attract digital and deep tech startups led by women. The open calls aim to collect more than +150 applications,

of which 25 of them will be selected to join the programme. The selection process will go through a well-tested four-step scouting methodology (Scout - Contact - Analyse Engage) to facilitate the engagement of the startup teams.

EmpoWomen programme was specifically designed to generate a network of women among tech founders and support them in building internationally sustainable companies. Overall, selected startups will have access to an all-in-one programme combining 1) equity-free funding; 2) acceleration services; and 3) vouchers, totaling 1.125.000 euros.

The project EmpoWomen is being managed by the internal consortium, spearheaded by Sploro. As a leader in cascade funding management, Sploro's founders have actively contributed to the Women TechEU initiative, attracting numerous organizations towards this idea. TechUkraine, a platform focused on supporting Ukraine's tech ecosystem, plays a crucial role in connecting with European ecosystems to rebuild their national ecosystem in the aftermath of war, as well as executes its key function - spreading important messages, both related to national objectives and also the pan-European ones. BAE, the principal federation of associations of business angels in Europe, has members such as business angels working in widening area countries. Additionally, Startup Wise Guys (SWG), a highly active startup investor and accelerator in Europe agreed to run acceleration for the selected startups. They have conducted 64 pre-accelerator programmes, engaging over 1,150 participants and co-investing with prominent Venture Capital firms like Presto Ventures, Speedinvest, Trind vc, and Specialist VC (formerly United Angels VC), among others.

Furthermore, the consortium has pledged to collaborate with various national associations in the widening area countries, offering access to their networks. This commitment aims to facilitate the dissemination and engagement of deep tech ventures in specific widening areas such as Latvia, Slovakia, the Canary Islands in Spain, Georgia, Croatia, Tunisia, Moldova, and Bulgaria.

II. Communication & Dissemination Plan

1. Introduction

Deliverable D4.1. delineates the communication and dissemination strategy tailored for the EmpoWomen Project, outlining the methodology and tools that all participating partners are required to employ to disseminate and communicate their activities.

In this deliverable we united communication and dissemination plans as they share common goals of spreading information, engaging stakeholders, and achieving project objectives. Combining communication and dissemination plans is a strategic approach that enhances the effectiveness of both activities. Integration enables a more targeted and audience-centric approach. This ensures that the right message is delivered through the most effective channels to reach the intended audience, maximizing visibility and

delivering the best results. Also, this unification means a synergy in messaging, key messages are coherent and aligned, which is crucial for delivering a unified narrative and avoiding confusion among the target audience.

This deliverable establishes common guidelines for communication and dissemination activities initiated since the project's inception and those planned for its entire lifecycle. It delineates key target audiences, and primary messages, and details the tools and channels to be utilized, tentative plans and calendars of events. The document delves into stakeholder engagement, subsequently assessing the indicators and targets established to evaluate the effectiveness of communication efforts.

2. Roles and Responsibilities of the Consortium Entities

The EmpoWomen consortium consists of four partners from four European countries (Spain, Ukraine, Belgium, and Estonia). It has been established to bring to the project a valuable background in methodologies and tools relevant to the project, and to incorporate several relevant areas of expertise of consortium and associated partners. Among associated partners from widening area countries there are – Latvijas Jaunuzņēmumu asociācija (Latvia), Slovenska Aliancia Pre Inovativnuekonomiku (Slovenia), Asociacion Canaria de Startups Empresas de Base Tecnologia e Inversores Angeles (Canarian Islands), National Startup Association of Georgia (Georgia), CRO Startup (Croatia), Smart Capital (Tunisia), Startup Moldova, Bulgarian Entrepreneurs and Startup Community (Bulgaria).

The expertise and value of each partner as well as their involvement in the communication and dissemination strategy of the project are outlined in Table 1.

Table 1.

Consortium Partners and their roles in communication and dissemination of the project.

Partner	Role in the project
SPLORO	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Project Coordination and Leadership in internal communication ensuring that all project components align with the programme's goals and timelines. 2. Communication of administrative and legal requirements to partners, ensuring compliance and efficient collaboration. 3. Communicate financial guidelines and procedures to partners, overseeing the 4. Communication of the use of the online platform (www.cascadefunding.sploro.eu) for application and evaluation processes. 5. Open Call Communication: making clear eligibility and criteria of open calls to potential applicants.

Partner	Role in the project
▶▶▶ SPLORO	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. Reporting and Documentation: communication of reporting requirements and expectations to partners for timely submission of project-related documentation. 7. Dissemination of the main news of the project on its social media.
TechUA	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Responsible for designing and executing the project's Communication and Dissemination strategy (WP4 leader). 2. Participation in the identification, scouting, and assessment of startups to participate in the Open Calls. 3. Communication of the project updates, milestones, and achievements to partners, stakeholders, media, and the broader community in the widening ecosystems.
SWG	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Participation in the identification, scouting, and assessment of startups to participate in the Open Calls. 2. Dissemination of the main news of the project on its social media. 3. Communication of the unique features of acceleration programme for women-led startups 4. Communication and promotion of the EmpoWomen programme among mentor network, experts in deep tech, VCs and investors.
BAE	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Participation in the selection process 2. Communication and promotion of the EmpoWomen programme among European BAs and their associations. 3. Communication of matchmaking events with Investors 4. Dissemination of the main news of the project on its social media.
Associated Partners	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identification, scouting, and assessment of startups to participate in the Open Calls. 2. Communication and dissemination of the main news of the project on social media, and awareness-raising activities.

Consortium partners: contribute to the communication and dissemination process by delivering content to the website and engaging and influencing all targeted key stakeholder groups. A Partner that intends to disseminate their news must give at least 15 days advance notice to the other Consortium partners, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other Partner may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate corrective steps are taken. Detailed procedure is explained in block 7.6. of this document ("Procedure for external communication").

Moreover, schedule of communication for social media aims to deliver weekly posts on the Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn pages of the EmpoWomen programme (detailed in the block “EmpoWomen Social Media”). All partners will follow these profiles and share updates on their respective pages. To enhance convenience for the partners, TechUA will send email notifications regarding recently published posts.

Responsibilities of consortium partners in the implementation of D.4.1:

Project Coordinator: monitors deliverables that are prepared in a proper and timely manner; tracks progress of the T4.1 and ensures milestones are reached and KPIs are met. SPLORO is the Project Coordinator.

WP Leader: is responsible for the execution of the WP4 and respective tasks and coordinates Task leaders; monitors the progress of the WP4 and respective tasks against the work plan and schedule; ensures that the work package fulfills the objectives and deliverables; reviews and evaluates the work package results and reports to the Project Coordinator. TechUA is WP Leader.

Task Leader: ensures the compliance of EmpoWomen communication and dissemination activities within the Objectives set for T4.1; develops communication and dissemination tools and coordinates communication activities. Tatiana Skydan from TechUA is the Task Leader.

3. Methodology

WP4 “Ecosystem Building & Exploitation”, led by TechUA, is dedicated to formulating a comprehensive communication and dissemination plan and strategy for the project for two years (2024-2025). Its primary goals encompass establishing the project's identity and communication channels, engaging stakeholders, fostering organic growth, engaging relevant startups into the programme, and refining the project's value proposition to facilitate sustainable exploitation of results.

Tasks 4.1, led by TechUA and involving all project participants, hold a pivotal role throughout the project's entire duration in 2024-2026. This task focuses on developing and implementing an all-encompassing dissemination and communication strategy, ensuring the broadest possible outreach of the project's activities and results at the pan-European level. This involves crafting and executing a dynamic dissemination plan, utilizing channels, measures, and tools that will be continually updated and synchronized with the ongoing project activities. The task also encompasses coordinating joint events with relevant initiatives and promoting the project to ensure its value proposition reaches the appropriate audience.

All activities in dissemination and communication align with the identified target groups and key performance indicators (KPIs) outlined in this section dedicated to measures to maximize impact. The strategy undergoes regular review and adaptation to maintain alignment with the project's overarching goals and objectives.

The tasks associated with the dissemination and communication activities include:

1. Communication and dissemination strategy and plan;
2. Logotype and visual identity for the project;
3. Elaboration of the key messages to specific target groups;
4. Development and management of communication tools (EmpoWomen website and Social media - Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook);
5. Administration of all social profiles, which means, publishing and controlling content and monitoring the suitability and relevance of the information to be published.
6. Production of agreed and quality-controlled communication and dissemination material such as website content, press releases, newsletters, etc.;
7. Media Relations: Press releases issued with media engagement and content pitching; published project materials and publications in peer review, press conferences (as needed) with the support of other consortium partners, and lead relations with EU and national media to ensure EmpoWomen is published in relevant publications and media outlets;
8. Ensuring dissemination at high-level conferences and events, networking with similar projects and international initiatives;

The Communication plan is documented in the present deliverable as an output of Task 4.1 and will be constantly updated by TechUA during the project implementation (M2 - M24) and will include the detailed planning of all communication activities of the EmpoWomen campaign and promotion systematically. The Communication Plan will be available via a link on Google disk.

Actual activities will be visible in the social media channels employed, as well as in the physical and digital materials produced and disseminated.

Developing a communication and dissemination plan involves outlining the methods and strategies for effectively conveying information to a target audience. The methodology needed for this plan consists of three phases:

Phase 1: Launch Preparation and Awareness (M1-M3)

1. Defining the Key Messages: crafting clear and impactful messages that resonate with the programme's mission, emphasizing empowerment in the tech industry.
2. Identification of Target Audience: definition and segmentation of the audience aligned with EmpoWomen's goals.
3. Establishment of Online Presence: creation of a dedicated website, and set up of social media profiles for updates and engagement.
4. Engagement of Influencers: collaboration with influencers in women empowerment and tech sectors to generate anticipation and pre-launch buzz.

5. Press Release and Media Outreach: development of a comprehensive press release and media outreach to gain coverage and visibility ahead of open calls and the programme launch.

Phase 2: Programme Launch and Initial Outreach (M3-M23)

1. The first Open Calls: intensive communication for two open calls – for participants and evaluators of the project.
2. Launch Event: hosting a launch event or webinar to officially introduce EmpoWomen, involving key stakeholders and showcasing programme features.
3. Content Creation: developing diverse content, including website articles, videos, and infographics, explaining programme goals, and participation opportunities.
4. Engagement of Partners and Ambassadors: collaboration with partners, ambassadors, and advocates to amplify the programme's reach and encourage information sharing.
5. Social Media Campaigns: launch targeted social media campaigns using engaging visuals and consistent messaging, employing appropriate hashtags for community engagement (#EmpoWomen, #women, #womenintech, #womenentrepreneurs, #deeptech)
6. Webinars and Workshops: organization of webinars and workshops to provide in-depth insights into the EmpoWomen programme, address questions, and encourage participation.

Phase 3: Programme Fulfillment and Expansion (M6-M24)

1. Regular Updates: maintaining of a consistent flow of updates through newsletters, social media, and the programme's website, highlighting achievements, success stories, and upcoming events.
2. The second Open Call: intensive communication for open calls for participants of the project.
3. Community Building: boosting a sense of community among EmpoWomen participants through online forums, discussion groups, and networking events.
4. Impact Measurement: collecting success stories and using data to demonstrate EmpoWomen's value to partners and stakeholders.
- 5.

This phased approach ensures a strategic and comprehensive communication and dissemination plan for the EmpoWomen programme, optimizing visibility, engagement, and impact.

Important note: Phase 2 and Phase 3 will run in parallel in a certain moment in time as shown in the diagram (Figure 1. Intersection of the programme's phases)

4. Procedures

Communicating effectively with partners is vital for the success of any programme. Here are procedures for communication with partners in the context of the EmpoWomen programme:

1. Onboarding: a comprehensive onboarding session to introduce consortium and associated partners to the EmpoWomen programme's mission, objectives, and key team members.

2. Communication Channels: set up communication channels to facilitate seamless and organized information exchange and provide feedback:

- **Email:** Partners may use email for formal communication, document sharing, and important announcements.
- **Instant Messaging/Chat:** Slack and Microsoft Teams for real-time communication, file sharing, and project updates.
- **Project Management Tools:** Google Calendar and Google Sheets for project-specific communication, task management, and collaboration.
- **Meetings:** Regular team meetings for discussing progress and addressing concerns. Detailed plan see in block 8.1. ("Consortium meetings").
- **Video Conferencing:** Platforms Zoom, Microsoft Teams, or Google Meet for face-to-face virtual meetings, which can enhance communication and collaboration.

3. External communication procedure is being realized by WP Leader (TechUA) via:

- EmpoWomen's Website, where contributors of content are all consortium members. Content Types: The website includes information about the programme, partner profiles, success stories, and upcoming events.
- Social Media posts crafted by a dedicated social media manager from the TechUA team. Partners may also be encouraged to contribute content or share programme-related updates. The tone used on social media aligns with the programme's branding and messaging. It's a positive, inclusive, and empowering tone that resonates with the target audience. Usage of hashtags #EmpoWomen, #women, #womenintech, #womenentrepreneurs, #deeptech encourage engagement and facilitate tracking of programme-related content.
- Newsletters and press releases are scheduled in the block 7.5.2. ("Online Dissemination Tools").
- Events: when partners attend events on behalf of the programme EmpoWomen, their actions and responsibilities can contribute to the programme's success and visibility. By attending events partners:
 - represent the programme
 - do networking and seek opportunities to connect with like-minded individuals or organizations that align with the programme's goals

- distribute promotional materials, such as brochures or business cards
- participate in panel discussions, workshops, or presentations related to the programme's focus
- collect feedback which can be valuable for refining and improving the programme.

4. Confidentiality and Data Protection: dealing with GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) is a critical aspect of managing the programme EmpoWomen. General guidelines on how the EmpoWomen programme addresses GDPR compliance are located on the website www.empowerment.eu in the block “Terms of services”.

By implementing these communication procedures, the EmpoWomen programme can cultivate strong partnerships, ensure effective collaboration, and collectively work toward the programme's objectives.

5. Obligations

Article 17 of the Grant Agreement outlines the following obligations on communications:

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text.

Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

Figure 2.

The European Union emblem for display

**Funded by
the European Union**

**Funded by
the European Union**

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text.

**Funded by
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When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the emblem without first obtaining approval from the granting authority. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

6. Objectives

The project EmpoWomen aims to share practical knowledge to boost the presence of women entrepreneurs in the deep-tech startup ecosystem and improve collaboration among startup ecosystems in the widening area. The communication and dissemination objectives include:

1. **Raise Awareness:** Share information about the open call and project-related activities.
2. **Attract Applicants:** Encourage applications from women-led deep-tech companies from widening-area countries for the programme.
3. **Build Credibility:** Establish EmpoWomen as a reputable initiative with the support of Sploro, TechUkraine, Startup Wise Guys, and Business Angels Europe.
4. **Promote Diversity:** Emphasize the importance of diversity in the deep-tech sector and highlight the potential impact of women-led companies.
5. **Build a Solid Network:** Connect different audience groups and stakeholders, establishing the project as a thought leader and a hub for growth/partnerships among female leaders in digital and deep tech, investors, corporates, networks, and more.
6. **Strengthen Partnerships:** Inform EU organizations about the opportunities for collaboration with the project, particularly in promoting women's entrepreneurship across Europe.
7. **Exploit Results:** Establish sustainable connections with pan-national, national, and regional authorities, as well as private sources (e.g., potential capital providers) to leverage project results and create lasting demand for products/services beyond the project's duration.

7. External Communication & Dissemination Plan

The EmpoWomen project's communication and dissemination strategy adheres to principles and best practices outlined in the EC Guidelines for successful communication

and dissemination. The primary focus is on identifying and mapping targeted stakeholders, understanding their needs, and tailoring clear messages. This ensures the use of effective dissemination channels and tools and the development of suitable materials for each stakeholder. The strategy also includes a time plan with specific objectives and target focuses for each project phase, aiding all project partners.

By implementing this communication and dissemination plan, the EmpoWomen programme aims to create a strong and impactful presence, attract the right participants, and contribute to the success of women-led deep-tech startups in widening-area countries.

7.1. Communication & Dissemination Activities for Open Calls

The crucial part of the programme is an open call. It's a period in which the open call is open to receive applications.

The first Open Call for applicants is scheduled for the 8th of January 2024, and the second one – for December 2024. Open Call for evaluators starts on the 22nd of January 2024.

The average duration of Open Calls will be two months as it is established in the EC rules for managing FSTP funds. During this period, promotional events and awareness-raising campaigns will be done to engage and attract applicants.

Effectively communicating and disseminating information about open calls for the EmpoWomen programme is important to attract qualified applicants and generate awareness.

The key communication and dissemination activities for open calls are:

1. 1Pre-registration for the programme in period M1-M3 is being communicated via social media of EmpoWomen (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn). Those who have interest in participating register here: <https://bit.ly/EmpoWOMEN> As Open Call starts all these applications will be redirected to the application form on the official website www.empowomen.eu
2. Launch Announcement: a compelling announcement detailing the launch of the open calls and its dissemination through various channels, including the programme's website, social media, press releases, and newsletters.
3. Targeted Email Campaigns designed to reach out to potential applicants, stakeholders, and partners, clearly outlining the open call details, eligibility criteria, and application process.
4. Social Media Campaigns across platforms Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn with engaging content, using relevant hashtags (#EmpoWomen, #women, #womenintech, #womenentrepreneurs, #deeptech) to maximize reach. Encouragement of the partners, influencers, and followers to share the posts. Also, the Open Call can be promoted on EISMEA's social media accounts.
5. Press Releases for relevant media outlets, tech blogs, and industry publications.

6. Email Newsletter providing links to detailed information, deadlines, and application instructions.
7. Community Engagement: sharing open call details with online communities, forums, and groups relevant to women in tech and entrepreneurship.

7.2. Communication & Dissemination Strategy for the Entire Project

All members of the consortium, along with associated partners and specialized media, will actively contribute to disseminating information to reach our target groups. EmpoWomen programme plans to employ a mix of methods, such as growth hacking and organically referenced communication, and various tools, including newsletters, social media, platforms, and events. This approach will leverage existing partnerships and networks to connect with beneficiaries across ecosystems of widening-area countries.

Each partner will leverage their pre-existing organizational channels, which already have an audience and followers (in total there are +67.600 LinkedIn, +13.000 Twitter, +67.000 Facebook, +6.000 Instagram) to push project messaging. Finally, EmpoWomen will capitalize on an existing community of over 50 organizations (including business networks, investors, women associations, universities, enterprises, and public institutions), that were involved in The European Gateway for Women's Entrepreneurship Initiative (WEgate), in which our project partner BAE was part of and the coordinator.

Communication efforts will kick off within the consortium and then extend through direct partner networks, as well as other associated networks and projects. For broader communication, the project will engage the media, run advertising campaigns, utilize PR strategies, and form partnerships with top events and startup networks.

The EmpoWomen project's communication and dissemination strategy will adhere to the principles and best practices outlined in the EC Guidelines for successful dissemination. The central focus of this strategy will be to identify and map targeted stakeholders (the audience for dissemination) while comprehending their needs and characteristics. This understanding will enable the customization of clear and concise messages (the content for dissemination). Additionally, the strategy ensures the use of the most suitable and efficient dissemination channels and communication tools, guiding the development of appropriate materials tailored for each target stakeholder (the method of dissemination). The strategy also includes a defined time plan, outlining when to disseminate, with specific objectives and target focuses for each phase. This structured approach aims to assist all project partners in their dissemination efforts. In order to maximize the impact of communication efforts:

- Activities need to be carried out on time
- Information used must be accurate
- Activities should be coordinated closely with the Consortium
- The right audience(s) should be targeted
- Messages should interest the target audience(s)
- Activities should be appropriate in terms of resources spent, timing and expected impact

7.3. Target Audience

At the core of the communication and dissemination plan lies a stakeholder analysis and mapping process, ensuring that the project's objectives and results effectively engage and reach all intended target audiences.

Table 2.
Target audience

Target Group	
FEMALE ENTREPRENEURS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Female Entrepreneurs Women-led Digital startups Women-led startups Women-led Spin-offs & RTOs 	<p>This category comprises organizations led by women actively involved in technological innovations, contributing to research, or conducting business activities relevant to the application of deep-tech innovations.</p>
STARTUP SUPPORT & INVESTORS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accelerators Incubators Investors (BA, VC, Corporate Ventures) 	<p>Incubators, accelerators, and business support organizations will enhance their capacities and adopt practices tailored to address the unique requirements of women entrepreneurs in the deep-tech sector. Furthermore, to maximize the opportunities for selected projects to attract additional funding, EmpoWOMEN will concentrate its communication efforts on capital providers, including investors in the forms of Business Angels, Venture Capitalists (VCs), Corporate VCs, or Industry Experts.</p>
INNOVATION & STARTUPS ECOSYSTEMS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Startups Associations Startup Networks EIC Widening Area Ecosystems 	<p>The project will utilize its consortium's influence to swiftly establish synergies with innovation ecosystems that house extensive networks of entrepreneurs in the specified countries. To date, 24 startup associations from widening ecosystems have been approached, with eight of them committing as associated partners and TechUA as a beneficiary. Their role is to contribute to identifying potential applicants and enhance the project's impact and outreach.</p> <p>Additionally, the project aims to engage with the following initiatives:</p> <p>Entrepreneurship initiatives such as Startup Europe or the EIC community, particularly focusing on the</p>

Target Group	
	<p>established community of the EIC Women TechEU programme; EU Digital Innovation Hubs; The Women Leadership Programme (WLP) community and the EIT, which supports a considerable number of female entrepreneurs within the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT).</p> <p>Moreover, the project intends to build upon the groundwork established in previous Startup Europe projects, transferring insights and leveraging accumulated knowledge for the success of the EmpoWOMEN programme.</p>
<p>POLICY MAKERS & SOCIETY</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Commission • Local Governments • Member states • Society as a whole 	<p>Government representatives, innovation ministries, or other organizations tasked with formulating new policies and advocating for strategies to enhance the involvement of women entrepreneurs will find value in this project. Policymakers can leverage the knowledge and outcomes generated, particularly in relation to the services programme, to enhance the current Women TechEU programme. Furthermore, the project will serve as a tool to advance gender equality across various aspects of life, with a particular focus on the entrepreneurial ecosystem, aligning with one of the key priorities of the European Commission.</p>
<p>TECH MEDIA</p>	<p>Providing tech journalists, reporters, and editors with access to programme leaders, participants, and success stories for interviews or feature articles can effectively raise awareness within the tech community and beyond, fostering support and participation in the programme.</p>

7.4. Focus for Communication Messages

Crafting key communication messages engages and resonates with the esteemed target audience. Rooted in the vision of empowerment and innovation, the messages aim to not just convey information but to forge meaningful connections inside and outside of the ecosystem.

Key Messages include:

Empower Women in Deep Tech: Highlight the commitment to overcoming barriers faced by women in R&D&I and fostering equality in deep tech entrepreneurship.

Exclusive Support: Communicate the unique features of the EmpoWomen programme, including the 2-year duration, non-repayable funding, prizes, and services for selected companies.

Strategic Partnerships: Emphasize the collaboration of Sploro, TechUkraine, Startup Wise Guys, Business Angels Europe and associated partners showcasing the strength of the initiative funded by the European Union.

Global Impact: Illustrate how supporting women-led companies contributes to the growth and leadership of the deep tech sector on a global scale.

7.5. Communication tools

EmpoWomen will employ a diverse set of tools and channels to effectively disseminate and communicate its activities and outcomes. Each tool and channel will be strategically selected to cater to distinct target groups across various project stages, enhancing the efficacy of the Communication and Dissemination Plan. The correlation between these tools, channels, target groups, and anticipated results is outlined in Table 3.

Table 3.
Communication approaches for different target groups

Channel	Tool	Purpose	KPI
Online	Website	Providing a complete overview of the project activities, displaying the latest updates. The web will be updated regularly, with news, showcasing the selected startups, achievements, and content extracted from the deliverables and reports. It will also be linked with the platform for Open Calls and cross-linked with partners' websites and other related projects and initiatives.	+300 unique visitors monthly
	Social Media	Utilize platforms like LinkedIn, Twitter, and Instagram for announcements, regular updates, success stories, and engagement with the community.	+2000 size of online community (by the end of the project)

Channel	Tool	Purpose	KPI
▶▶▶ Online	Social Media	Provisional schedule of communications on social media corresponding to the phases of the programme – in the block “EmpoWomen Social Media”.	+12000 impressions in total by the end of the project)
	Newsletter	Send targeted emails to potential applicants, partners, and stakeholders.	+6
	Press Releases	Issue press releases to key media outlets in the startup, innovation, and business sectors.	+6
	Publications in Media	Bring attention to the transformative nature of the EmpoWomen programme and its significant contributions through stories, and insightful interviews.	+30
	Podcasts	Arrange interviews with programme leaders, mentors, and successful women entrepreneurs.	+20
Events	Workshops, webinars (offline, online)	Facilitate the exchange of knowledge and experiences.	+30
	Events organized by EmpoWomen	Extend the reach and impact of the programme	+10
	External events attended by EmpoWomen	Promote the programme and raise awareness about women in tech.	+5

7.5.1. EmpoWomen Visual Identity

A recognizable project identity has been developed to build a visual brand. This includes a logo and style guide that will be used consistently on the project website and in all communication materials like PowerPoint and Word document templates. More details are in **Annex 1**.

7.5.2. Online Dissemination Tools

a) EmpoWomen Website

The project website is the main communication and dissemination platform to allow stakeholders, policymakers, and media access to the project development and results launched and developed. It will also host all the public dissemination deliverables, and

promote relevant content (news, interview highlights, events, etc.) for the key stakeholder groups, engaging them in the content and objectives of the project. The website will also serve as a content generation tool where partners are welcome to contribute content and provide feedback on its development to help increase the visibility of the project and maximize its impact. The key aim of the website is to serve as the primary reference point for EmpoWomen, to explain the project’s aims, provide the latest news updates, provide documents for download, and view social media activity related to the project.

The proposed domain of the website is www.empowomen.eu.

Website efficiency will be underpinned by the criteria of:

- Usability. The clear and accessible structure
- Content updating by TechUA
- Accuracy in the content suitability

The working language of the website is English.

The Website map has been designed to offer a complete overview of the project and easy access to all its activities.

Figure 3.
EmpoWomen website components

After the project’s conclusion the website will be online for 3 more years, or further if requested for continuation. During that period the materials and results of the project will be available for Project Participants and for the public.

Figure 4.
EmpoWomen website style

b) EmpoWomen Social Media

Social media has emerged as a widely embraced tool for swiftly sharing information among diverse audience groups. These platforms provide instant access to content, accessible anytime and anywhere, through various digital devices. In a strategic move to broaden the project's audience, with a specific focus on engaging the general public beyond sector experts, EmpoWomen is strategically incorporating these media tools into its communication activities. These tools deepen audience engagement, ensuring continuous updates and connection to the project. For promoting project achievements, news, and outcomes, Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn have been identified as the most suitable social networks.

Figure 5.
Social Media accounts

TWITTER	
<p>Name: EmpoWomen Programme</p> <p>Account: @empowomen</p> <p>Link: https://twitter.com/empowomen</p>	
LINKEDIN	
<p>Name: EmpoWomen Programme</p> <p>Account: @empowomen-programme</p> <p>Link: https://www.linkedin.com/company/empowomen-programme</p>	

EmpoWomen's profiles on these social networks aim to reflect the key updates on the EmpoWomen website. The most significant content, particularly news, events, and partners' activities, will be shared on these profiles to reach a broader audience. EmpoWomen plans to achieve organic growth by leveraging its social media and online presence, along with the communication channels of consortium members and their partners. This approach relies on collaborative online media dissemination by partners to ensure a reach to widening areas, coupled with specific strategies targeting both online and offline audiences.

Creating a schedule of communication on social media involves planning content strategically to maintain engagement and share updates consistently. Here's a provisional schedule that spans 12 months of the first year of the programme and corresponds to its phases:

Table 4.
Schedule of communication on social media in the first year of the programme (M1-M12)

Month of the programme	Topics for the content
Month 1-2: Launch and Introduction	Programme launch across all social media platforms. Introduction of consortium members and programme objectives.
Month 3-4: Open Calls & Programme Features	Announcement of open calls with specific details. Eligibility for applications. Feature highlights of the online platform for applications and evaluation. In-depth feature of the benefits and unique opportunities for participants. Q&A session to address queries about the application process.

Month of the programme	Topics for the content
Month 5-6: Projects Evaluation & Startups Selection	<p>In-depth look at the criteria used to evaluate project proposals and startups.</p> <p>Introduction of the panel of evaluators responsible for assessing project proposals.</p> <p>Highlight the diverse backgrounds and ideas represented in the selected startups.</p> <p>Introduction of the profiles of the selected startups.</p>
Month 7-8: Start of acceleration programme	<p>Key components and values of the acceleration programme.</p> <p>Introduction of the mentors.</p> <p>Overview of deep tech industry and role of female leaders.</p>
Month 9-10: Mid-Programme Updates and Community Building	<p>Updates and insights from participants' journey in the acceleration programme.</p> <p>Progress, achievements and upcoming events.</p> <p>Recognition and appreciation for partners and contributors.</p>
Month 11-12: Programme Success Stories and Achievements	<p>Success stories of participants and their impact on deep tech industry.</p> <p>Overview of innovations developing in the startups.</p> <p>Coverage of Final Demo Day and summary of the presentations.</p> <p>Main insights of the first year of EmpoWomen Programme.</p> <p>Announcement for the second Open Call.</p>

The content plan corresponding to this schedule of communication is located on Google disk and being constantly updated. This figure demonstrates planning and topics for the first month of the EmpoWomen programme:

Figure 6.
Content plan for M1-M4 on social media.

Phase	Month // Topic	About project	About women in tech	About partners	About events in tech	About acceleration programme	Ecosystems in Widening Areas	Deep Tech Innovations	Success Stories
Month 1: Launch and Introduction	November 2023 (NO SOCIAL MEDIA YET)								
Month 2: Launch and Introduction	December 2023	press release	% of women in tech	consortium					
		open call							
Month 3: Open Calls & Program Features	January 2024	open call for applicants							famous women in deep tech
		call for evaluators		about SWG about BAE		unique features	prominent ecosystems		
Month 4: Open Calls & Program Features	February 2024	eligibility			upcoming events	programme plan			
		evaluation procedure		associated partners					

c) EmpoWomen Newsletter

The newsletter will ensure both communication and dissemination at different levels – local and EU – and will keep the stakeholders up to date with the findings of the project, inform about other relevant events, publications, key policy developments, and key messages of the project partners.

The consortium foresees the production of semi-annual digital newsletters during the project, whose purpose will be to raise awareness of the project and its latest news. To ensure national dissemination and impact, the Newsletters will be translated into the partners' languages (Spanish, Ukrainian, Georgian, Latvian, Slovenian, Moldavian, and other languages of widening countries) by the associated partners in these countries. Moreover, each national Newsletter could be customized with particular articles, news, or events relevant at the national level. These newsletters will be sent proactively to the database of stakeholders to be built during the project, and it will also be possible for interested parties to subscribe via the web platform.

Newsletters will provide regular communication to subscribers and guarantee the message is delivered to them directly by email. With this channel EmpoWomen will keep the stakeholders up to date with the findings of the project, inform them about other relevant events, and publications, and communicate specific goals and tasks to targeted audiences, thus enhancing the interest of particular partners and creating call-to-action messages.

Contributions to the EmpoWomen newsletter will be open to all project partners. As within two years of the project, six newsletters are planned, SPLORO, TechUA, SWG, and BAE will exchange updated information aligned with phases of the programme and newsletters' themes.

The newsletters' topics:

1. Launch of the programme & Open Call
2. Acceleration programme by SWG & BAE
3. Meet participants of EmpoWomen programme
4. Outcomes of the first year of the EmpoWomen programme & Open Call 2
5. Success stories of women in deep-tech
6. Outcomes of the second year of the EmpoWomen programme

A newsletter will be broadcasted by email to the free online subscribers to spread the work of the project.

The proposed structure of each newsletter is:

- Introduction to newsletter
- Project update | Key news highlights, deliverables
- News & Events (internal, external)
- Resources for further reading

d) Press releases

Press releases will be issued by all partners during the project coinciding with important milestones like local or European events, the launch of open calls, start and progress of the acceleration programme, and project achievements.

Press releases will be targeted at key players (e.g. women entrepreneurs and ecosystem builders, investors, policymakers and local authorities, startups, and supporting organizations). The communication team will actively follow up on the releases to assure maximum coverage.

Table 5.
Tentative calendar for newsletters and press releases in 2024

	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
Newsletter			X			X						X
Press Release	X			X			X			X		

Table 6.
Tentative calendar for newsletters and press releases in 2025

	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
Newsletter			X				X				X	
Press Release				X						X		

e) Webinars

Webinars play a crucial role in the EmpoWomen programme, offering a necessary and dynamic platform for applicants. The significance of scheduled 30 webinars lies in several key aspects:

Webinars provide a convenient and accessible way for potential applicants to engage with the EmpoWomen programme. Participants can join from anywhere, overcoming geographical barriers.

Through webinars, detailed information about the programme, application process, and eligibility criteria can be effectively communicated. This ensures that applicants receive comprehensive insights, fostering a clear understanding of what the programme entails.

Webinars enable interactive learning experiences. Applicants can actively participate in Q&A sessions, and discussions, and receive real-time clarifications, enhancing their understanding of the programme requirements.

The live and interactive nature of webinars helps to engage applicants on a personal level. It creates a sense of community and motivation as participants connect with programme organizers, mentors, and potential future collaborators.

Webinars offer flexibility in scheduling, accommodating applicants with varying time zones and busy schedules. This flexibility ensures inclusivity and allows a broader range of individuals to participate. Webinars provide a platform to guide applicants through the application process, offering tips, insights, and best practices. This guidance enhances the quality of applications and increases the likelihood of success.

Webinars contribute to the formation of a community of applicants. This sense of community fosters collaboration, knowledge sharing, and creates a supportive environment for aspiring women entrepreneurs in the deep tech sector.

In essence, webinars are essential for applicants to the EmpoWomen programme as they serve as an inclusive, informative, and engaging channel, ensuring that potential participants are well-informed, motivated, and equipped to submit strong applications.

The content of the webinars for the EmpoWomen programme is designed to serve specific objectives aligned with the programme's mission. The webinars aim to provide valuable insights, guidance, and support to the programme participants, partners, and the broader community interested in women's empowerment in the tech industry. The topics covered in these webinars may include:

1. Techniques and strategies for empowering women in the tech sector
2. Tech Industry Insights
3. Overview of trends and challenges in the technology industry
4. Opportunities for women-led startups and professionals
5. Success Stories
6. EmpoWomen Programme Updates and Opportunities: Information about upcoming opportunities, events, and open calls
7. Skill Development Workshops
8. Networking and Collaboration

Webinars will be held via Zoom or live events on LinkedIn and recorded for future reference and accessibility.

Among hosts and presenters, there will be knowledgeable experts, industry leaders, programme coordinators, and successful women in deep-tech.

The recorded webinars will be disseminated through various channels, such as the programme's official website, social media platforms, and partner networks.

f) Podcasts

Podcasts are one of impactful communication tools that have gained significant popularity in recent years. Podcasts allow to create engaging and informative content that resonates with their target audience. The conversational format encourages listeners to connect with the content on a deeper level.

Moreover, podcasts offer listeners the flexibility to consume content on their terms, whether during commutes, workouts, or leisure time. This accessibility increases engagement and extends the reach of the communication efforts. Podcasts transcend geographical boundaries, allowing the EmpoWomen programme to reach a global audience. This broad reach enables the programme to connect with women from diverse backgrounds, cultures, and regions, including widening area countries.

Starting from M7 of EmpoWomen programme TechUA will produce, record, and kick off the podcast series with an exclusive interviews with the visionary leaders behind the programme, mentors and professionals, female leaders actively involved in the EmpoWomen. Distribution of the podcast will be on Apple Podcasts, Spotify, Simplecast and other podcast platforms.

7.5.3. Offline Dissemination Tools

The most efficient approach to fortify a network and synchronize a group's endeavors toward a common objective is through internal meetings and events, which not only serve as a means of consolidation but also play a pivotal role in promoting the programme and engaging participants. Simultaneously, actively attending and participating in external events becomes the most effective method to expand a network, enhance programme visibility, and foster active engagement among participants.

The best way to grow a network is by attending and participating in external events.

a) External events

The EmpoWomen consortium members will have a presence at major startup events such as VivaTechnology, Slush, Web Summit, and more. Consortium members will actively participate as co-organizers, partners, or speakers at various community events, presenting ample opportunities to showcase and promote the EmpoWomen project and its activities. For broader global outreach, all partners will allocate resources to participate in and disseminate the EmpoWomen project at external third-party events tailored to potential EmpoWomen audience groups and aligned with EmpoWomen objectives.

External events refer to gatherings organized by parties outside the consortium, with the following objectives:

- Disseminate EmpoWomen project activities and achievements.
- Execute specific tasks to deepen cooperation within target groups and foster strong mutual relationships.
- Facilitate active exchange with all stakeholders by soliciting feedback, suggestions, and recommendations.
- Engage the community in expanding and leveraging results beyond the consortium and local ecosystems.

When partners attend events on behalf of the programme EmpoWomen, their actions and responsibilities contribute to the programme's success and visibility.

Table 7.
Tentative calendar of external events in 2024

	Event	Date	Place
1	Research and Innovation Week	March, 18-21, 2024	Brussels, Belgium
2	The Next Web	June, 20-21, 2024	Amsterdam. Netherlands
3	VivaTechnology	May, 22-25	Paris, France
4	WebSummit	November, 2024	Lisbon, Portugal

b) Self-organized events

The organization of events to promote the EmpoWomen programme in widening areas is a strategic initiative to extend the reach and impact of the programme. 10 events are tentatively planned and will be executed in regions designated as widening areas, aiming to engage and empower women in the deep tech sector. Through these gatherings, EmpoWomen seeks to:

Raise Awareness: Events serve as platforms to raise awareness about the EmpoWomen programme, its objectives, and the opportunities it offers to women in widening areas.

Network Building: The events facilitate networking opportunities, bringing together women entrepreneurs, stakeholders, and key players in the deep tech ecosystem. This fosters connections and collaboration within the widening areas.

Capacity Building: Workshops, seminars, and training sessions are often integrated into these events to enhance the skills and capacities of women in deep tech, empowering them to thrive in their entrepreneurial pursuits.

Community Engagement: The events are designed to actively involve the local community, encouraging support and participation. This engagement contributes to the sustainable growth of women-led ventures in widening areas.

Showcasing Success Stories: Successful women entrepreneurs and leaders are often featured as keynote speakers, sharing their journeys and accomplishments. This not only inspires participants but also highlights the potential for success within the EmpoWomen programme.

Collaboration with Local Ecosystems: Events provide an opportunity to collaborate with local ecosystems, leveraging existing networks and resources to maximize the programme's impact in widening areas.

By strategically organizing events in widening areas, the EmpoWomen programme aims to create a ripple effect, empowering women, fostering innovation, and contributing to the overall growth of the deep tech sector in these regions.

Table 8.

Tentative calendar of self-organized events in 2024-2025

	Event	Date	Place
1	Workshop 1 “Women in Tech”	April 2024	Istanbul, Turkey (TBC)
2	Workshop 2 “Women in Tech”	October 2025	Riga, Latvia (TBC)
3	Workshop 3 “Women in Tech”	January 2025	Sofia, Bulgaria (NDC)

7.6. Procedure for external communication

All project partners are expected to support dissemination, to ensure that stakeholders will be engaged throughout the lifetime of the project. Partners' activities may include but are not limited to: sharing content about the project on social media and on each company's own newsletter and website, engaging with relevant national and local media and with stakeholders. The partners will gather all these actions on a shared file that will be updated every month. In addition, all the partners must proactively share information with TU about their activities related to the project, such as attendance at conferences, as well as the project's developments and results.

Table 9.

EmpoWomen event calendar template

	Partner	Event	Date and place	Link content
1				
2				
3				

The external partners will act as intermediaries and strengthen EmpoWomen outreach capacity and communication impacts toward the target groups across a widening area countries.

8. Internal Communication & Dissemination Plan

Internal communication is key to an efficient and smooth execution of the project whilst maximizing the results. For this agreed to maintain work of:

- consortium meetings
- a common online platform (Sharepoint) for the management of dissemination and communication activities
- regular email updates from the communication package lead
- regular conference calls to exchange project information, update progress, and share results

The communication package lead recommends and requests that each respective partner from the consortium assign a 'communication ambassador' (contact person) to coordinate both internal and external communication needs and targets to maximize the impact and effectiveness of the project goals. Ambassadors play a vital role in making the project a success because they have the power to put the multiplier effect into practice.

8.1. Consortium Meetings

To ensure effective communication and coordination among the members, three consortium meetings will be held during the EmpoWomen project's lifespan.

The first meeting, serving as the kick-off event, took place on 20-21 November 2023 in Pamplona, Spain, and was hosted by the Project Coordinator. This gathering allowed consortium members to meet in person, fostering a shared understanding of the project's objectives and goals.

The second General Assembly meeting is scheduled to occur in Brussels, Belgium, in March 2024, close to the dates of EIT Summit and R&I Days happening these days in Brussels. This meeting aims to provide an update on the project's progress, address any challenges, and plan for future actions.

Through these meetings, the EmpoWomen project strives to nurture collaboration, facilitate idea exchange, and encourage mutual learning among its consortium members.

Table 10.

Tentative calendar of internal events

Meeting	Month	Location	Organizer
First in-person kick-off meeting	M1 November 2023	Pamplona, Spain	SPLORO
Second General assembly meeting	M6 March 2024	Brussels, Belgium	BAE
Third General assembly meeting	M12 October 2024	Malaga, Spain	SWG
Fourth General assembly meeting	M18 April 2025	TBC	TBC
Fifth General assembly meeting	M24 October 2025	TBC	TBC

8.2. Internal rules and procedures for the proper use of communication tools

Multiple campaigns are planned based on the EmpoWomen project's specific objectives. These campaigns can be tailored to meet various needs and can include the following:

- **Project Announcements:** Share important project updates, milestones, and major announcements with our audience.
- **Project Results Dissemination:** A campaign centered around effectively communicating and disseminating the outcomes, and achievements of the EmpoWomen project.
- **Meet the Partners Campaign:** A dedicated campaign to introduce and showcase our project partners, highlighting their expertise and contributions.
- **Interview Highlights Campaign:** This campaign will focus on sharing insightful interviews with heroines and providing valuable perspectives.
- **Events-Related Campaigns:** Campaigns that generate awareness, encourage participation, and foster collaboration in our events.
- **Resources-acknowledgement campaigns:** Share EmpoWomen elaboration of a pool of resources for supporting female entrepreneurial initiatives and deep tech start-ups led by women.

8.2. General rules for the content publishing

The material is to be provided by the Task Leader or a Consortium Partner as a link to an online document (content plan) with all required for the post details, including but not limited to a link to partners' website, logo, photo of interviewed person, etc. within pre-approved timelines. The document should be stored in the shared to all consortium members' folder.

The consortium provides their comments by the time of preapproved "comments required". If the Consortium does not provide any comments/corrections, the material is considered as sufficient for publishing at the preapproved time.

After the comments, the Task Leader or a Consortium Partner corrects their material as per suggestions. The Task Leader publishes the final material at the approved time without additional check/corrections/reminders.

It means that the material under the link at the time for the final version will be considered finalized and be published without any further corrections.

The material published on the Project Website is at the same time reposted by the Task Leader to the Project's social media account.

The material published on the Project Website should be if applicable reposted by Partners to the Partners' websites and social media. The Task Leader shares the links to all publications in the content plan so that every Partner can easily use the content for further dissemination.

8.3. Working internal templates

Another important asset in terms of communication activity within the project is to have homogeneous formats related to project deliverables, documents, presentations or any other item eventually produced. For this purpose, TU has produced different templates available for EmpoWomen partners in main formats: .doc (for documents and deliverables) and .ppt (for EmpoWomen presentations).

Figure 7.
Deliverable template

Figure 8.
Letterhead template

Figure 9:
Powerpoint Presentation template

EMPOWOMEN

Your Excellent Presentation

EMPOWOMEN

Your Excellent Presentation

Column and picture

Subtitle

It's no secret that people are the most important asset of any organization. Meet the team that makes it their mission to put you first. We make extra room in the budget without compromising quality by selling online and delivering directly to you.

We invent and create beautiful brands, digital products, and other most relevant digital things and we always try to provide the best services for all our clients.

Title and Six Columns

Something 1	Something 2	Something 3
The place for a short and laconic description of something	The place for a short and laconic description of something	The place for a short and laconic description of something in three lines for example. It can be absolutely any information
Something 4	Something 5	Something 6
The place for a short and laconic description of something in three lines for example. It can be absolutely any information	The place for a short and laconic description of something	The place for a short and laconic description of something

9. General Dissemination Plan

To summarize the written above communication and dissemination strategy it's crucial to detailize a dissemination aims and measures to ensure the success and widespread impact of the programme. This plan outlines target audiences and channels through which information about the EmpoWomen Programme will be shared to maximize the visibility of the project. Here is a general overview of the dissemination plan:

Table 11.

Dissemination for target groups

Dissemination for different target groups		
Target Group	Aims	Measures and channels:
FEMALE ENTREPRENEURS Female Entrepreneurs Women-led Digital startups Women-led startups Women-led Spin-offs & RTOs	<p>To encourage to apply and participate in the EmpoWomen programme;</p> <p>To empower and support women entrepreneurs in deep tech by providing them with the necessary tools, networks, and opportunities to thrive in the business world;</p> <p>To promote the growth and success of women-led companies by facilitating access to relevant resources, mentorship, and a network of support within the digital entrepreneurship ecosystem.</p>	Website Newsletter Public deliverables published on the website Social media: Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn Media clippings Webinars Events Podcasts
STARTUP SUPPORT & INVESTORS Accelerators Incubators Investors (BA, VC, Corporate Ventures)	<p>To contribute to the creation of a more inclusive and dynamic entrepreneurial landscape, unlocking the full potential of women entrepreneurs and driving innovation and economic growth;</p> <p>To create a supportive ecosystem within investment, accelerator, and incubator communities that actively encourages and champions women-led ventures, breaking down barriers and biases;</p> <p>To facilitate equal access to financial resources, mentorship, and networking opportunities for women-led startups, ensuring a level playing field for all entrepreneurs.</p>	Website Newsletter Public deliverables published on the website Social media: Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn Publications aimed at an expert audience Project summary brochures Information in the media Networking events Podcasts

Dissemination for different target groups		
Target Group	Aims	Measures and channels:
<p>INNOVATION & STARTUPS ECOSYSTEMS</p> <p>Startups Associations Startup Networks EIC Widening Area Ecosystems</p>	<p>To improve access to essential resources such as funding, mentorship, and networking opportunities for women entrepreneurs in widening areas;</p> <p>To establish mentorship networks that connect experienced mentors with women entrepreneurs in widening areas, fostering a supportive community and facilitating knowledge transfer;</p> <p>To catalyze positive change, creating a more inclusive and vibrant entrepreneurial landscape that empowers women to contribute significantly to economic development and community growth.</p>	<p>Website Newsletter Public deliverables published on the website Social media: Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn Publications aimed at an expert audience Project summary brochures Information in the media Networking events Podcasts</p>
<p>POLICY MAKERS & SOCIETY</p> <p>European Commission Local Governments Member states Society as a whole</p>	<p>To advocate for the formulation and implementation of policies that promote gender equality, particularly within the realms of entrepreneurship, education, and employment;</p> <p>To create an environment that encourages and supports women-led companies in deep tech sector;</p> <p>To boost an environment that encourages women and girls to pursue education and careers in STEM and other traditionally male-dominated fields;</p> <p>To support collaborations with non-governmental organizations, private sector entities, and international organizations to leverage resources and expertise in implementing gender-responsive policies;</p> <p>To raise public awareness about gender equality and the importance of women's empowerment, aiming to create a societal shift in attitudes and perceptions.</p>	<p>Website Newsletter Public deliverables published on the website Social media: Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn Publications aimed at an expert audience Project summary brochures Information in the media Networking events Podcasts</p>

Dissemination for different target groups		
Target Group	Aims	Measures and channels:
TECH MEDIA	<p>To increase the visibility and representation of women in technology by featuring their success stories, achievements, and contributions through tech media;</p> <p>To feature and highlight technological innovations, products, and services developed by women, emphasizing their creativity and impact on the industry;</p> <p>To cover empowerment programmes, workshops, and mentorship initiatives designed to support and uplift women in technology.</p>	<p>Regular press releases</p> <p>Events open to the press</p> <p>Interviews / Podcasts</p>

10. Evaluation and monitoring of communication & dissemination activities

Communication & dissemination activities will be monitored and evaluated according to a set of quantitative and qualitative success indicators. The evaluation of communication activities will determine the degree to which the communication objectives have been reached, and the relationship between the outcomes and the efforts made to reach the goals. This analysis will help the project to better understand facilitators and barriers to successful communication and will serve to refine the communication activities accordingly. These indicators comprise:

Table 12.
Communication and Dissemination KPIs

Activity	Indicator	Target
Project Website	No. of unique visitors (monthly average)	+300
Social Media	Total reach (impressions by the end of the project)	+120 000
Publications	No. of publications	+30
Press Releases	No. of press releases	+6
Newsletters	No. of newsletters contributed/released	+6
Podcasts	No. of tech talks/podcast episodes with female founders	+20
Webinars	No. of webinars organized	+30

Activity	Indicator	Target
Interviews with heroines	No. success stories generated and promoted (end of the project)	18
Printed Materials	No. of hard copies (i.e., flyers) distributed	+2 500
Self-organized Events	No. of self-organized events	+10
External Events	No. of external events we expect to participate	5

These indicators will be tracked by:

- Application Numbers: tracking the number and quality of applications received.
- Web Analytics: monitoring website traffic, engagement, and application conversions.
- Media Coverage: measuring the extent and impact of media coverage through press clippings and online mentions.
- Participant Success: tracking the progress and success of women-led companies throughout and after the programme.

By employing these methods, the EmpoWomen programme aims to gather comprehensive data on the reach, engagement, and impact of its communication and dissemination efforts. These metrics will provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of the strategies employed, helping to refine communication and dissemination strategy during the programme realization.

III. Conclusion

In conclusion, the suggested communication and dissemination strategy and plan for the EmpoWomen programme is designed to be comprehensive and impactful. By implementing these steps, the EmpoWomen programme aims to create a strong and impactful presence, unite efforts of all stakeholders, attract the right participants, and contribute to the empowerment and success of women-led deep-tech startups and businesses in widening-area countries.

Annex 1 - Project Identity

Project Logo

Figure 10.
EmpoWomen logotype

Logo

Icon

The EmpoWomen logotype consists of a logomark made of the letter W uniting the words “empower” and “women”. In the full-coloured version letter W has two colors – green and violet which reinforces the message of the logo and underscores the brand's commitment to empower women.

The font is confident, calm, neat, and simple. Writing in uppercase letters creates an emotion of power and growth, which is substantial for transferring ideas of providing opportunities for women in technologies and entrepreneurship.

The Logotype Versions

Figure 11.
Logotype versions

Coloured version

The gradient and black logo is the preferred one, and should be used whenever possible. There are other colours that can also be used if needed. In any case, all of them must be used on white/light background and white version on black background.

Logo and payoff

The EmpoWomen logo can be use with the following payoff, both side by side and stacked. Theses versions can be used with any other colours included in the EmpoWomen primary colour palette. Please avoid them whenever the payoff is too small to be legible.

Annotated Grant Agreement Block

To acknowledge the EU funding and branding, the EU flag and a reference text must accompany the use of the EmpoWomen logo. The following branding references are some examples that will be used for EmpoWomen publications and materials.

Figure 12.

Logotype and EU funding emblem

Typography

EmpoWomen uses Proxima Nova as the main typography. It comes in a variety of weights offering flexible use. Proxima Nova is used for titles, subtitles, and highlights and for a regular paragraph of text.

Proxima Nova Bold is used for titles.

Proxima Nova SemiBold is used for subtitles and highlights.

Proxima Nova Regular is used for body copy.

As an alternative when is not possible to use the above typography, Roboto or Arial can be used for headings, and for body copy.

Color Palette

The colours palette consists of logo palette (used for logo gradient only) primary and secondary palettes. These fresh colours were chosen to convey harmony and confidence in our brand. The chart shows the code of the colours making up the palette in different colour systems. As to ensure that the colour palette fits the specific characteristics of the different media that will be used to communicate and disseminate the project activities and results, the following assignment must be used:

- CMYK: for hard copy printing (roll-ups, leaflets, ...).
- RGB: for screen applications (powerpoint, word, ...).
- HEX: for web applications (website).

Logo palette

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Primary palette

	CMYK: 50, 55, 0, 0. RGB: 146, 124, 184. HEX: #927cb8	Gradient Angle 55% Slider to 50%		
	CMYK: 25, 35, 0, 0. RGB: 199, 176, 213. HEX: #c7b0d5			

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